

Work-Life Balance of Employees: An Organizational Context of Middle East

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Abstract

The imbalance between working hours and personal hours with reduction in the later has emphasized on the importance of the work-life balance programs that can facilitate employees to maintain balance and address conflicts of demands from workplace and personal and social life. After a decade passed, and many economies recovering from the economic downturn, it is important to explore whether the pressures on work-life balance has reduced and if companies are now resuming to increase facilities for employees in terms of work-life balance. Within this context, this study aimed to investigate work-life balance of employees in the Middle East countries and to explore the role of local businesses in facilitating employees to maintain work-life balance. Within the quantitative framework, a survey was conducted among 308 employees to explore their perception about work-life balance and support from their employers to achieve work-life balance. The results indicate that the work-life balance of employees is disturbed. There is increased workload, long working hours which in turn cause stress and tiredness. The employees are unable to manage family and social life and maintain adequate level of leisure and sporting activities even though sport and leisure activities are less important concern of employees. The research also concludes that there is high rate of employee turnover intention. Furthermore, there is also lack of support from Middle East employers. Employees are not engaged and involved in determination of work load and work schedules. There is also a need to improve leave and vacation policies. The SEM results indicate that employees in the organizational context are mainly concerned with time for family and social surroundings, changing their jobs if their current employers do not meet their requirements, longer working hours, and determination to their job tasks even though it is not necessary sometimes.

Keywords: *Work-life balance, Employer support, Family life, Employees.*

I. Introduction

According to Naithani, (2009) there has been an increase in the work demands in the second half of the 20th century, which ultimately reduced time available for family and personal leisure and relaxation. The imbalance between working hours and personal hours with reduction in the later has emphasized on the importance of the work-

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life balance programs that can facilitate employees to maintain balance and address conflicts of demands from workplace and personal and social life. In the early years of 21st century, there has been a significant increase in the number of programs developed by employers to facilitate employees to maintain work-life balance but as the economic downturn hit the world the demands from work life increase to a degree that the growth in the programs for work-life balance interrupted severely. A large number of companies, under the disguise of cost efficiency stopped investment and expenses on work-life balance programs and facilities (Naithani, 2009).

After a decade passed, and many economies recovering from the economic downturn, it is important to explore whether the pressures on work-life balance has reduced and if companies are now resuming to increase facilities for employees in terms of work-life balance. Within this context, this study aims to conduct research on work-life balance of employees in the Middle East and to explore the role of local businesses in facilitating employees to maintain work-life balance. The main research aim for this research report is to analyze the work-life balance of employees in the Middle East countries. Furthermore, as secondary aim this report will also analyze the role of employers in facilitating employees in Middle east to achieve adequate work-life balance.

1.1 Research Objectives

- To analyze the importance of work-life balance for employees
- To understand the impact of work-life imbalance on employees
- To explore the perception of employees regarding their work-life balance
- To analyze the role of employer programs on employees' work-life balance
- To identify the impact of employer programs on work-life balance of employees in the

Middle East.

II. Literature Review

2.1 Work-life Balance

There is significant literature in which a variety of definitions have been put forward has. However, a review conducted by Agha, Azmi, and Irfan, (2017) showed that many of the reviews regarding work-life balance either ignore to define work-life balance or if they do they fail to present explicit definition. Therefore, there is scarcity of studies that explore the construct and notion of work-life balance. Furthermore, there are various approaches to define and operationalize the term work-life balance and to obtain measurable working definitions which make it difficult to present a universally agreed definition. Some of the commonly cited definitions in the literature are presented in this section. Agha & Khan, (2019) defined work-life balance as the degree or reflection of orientation of an individual across different life roles. Hans, et al., (2015) defined work-life balance as the degree to which an individual is able to engage and satisfied both his work requirements and personal life requirements. Taiwo, Catherine, and Esther, (2016) defined work-life balance from a different perspective and concluded that it is the experience of an individual regarding all life domains and the way he/she devotes personal resources such as time, energy, and commitment to optimize experience in all life domains. Akinyele, Peters, and Akinyele, (2016) presented a simpler definition and

argued that work-life balance is the effectiveness of an individual towards family and work roles and the degree of success in these roles.

2.2 Impact of Work-life Balance

The work-life balance has significant impact on the mental and physical health and wellbeing of person. According Naithani, (2016) imbalance between professional and personal life leads to constant pressure on an individual which in turn is likely to transform into stress. Continuous stress leads to depression and nervous breakdowns. According to Akinyele, Peters, and Akinyele, (2016) work-life balance is critical for health of a person. Every individual must have adequate time to spend with family, in sporting and leisure activities, and to maintain personal health and hygiene.

On the other hand, literature shows that imbalance in personal and professional life has significant impact on productivity and performance of an individual. Continuous mental stress and possible depression leads to demotivation and burn out. Consequently, the ability of the person to work effectively is compromised leading to a severe decrease in individual productivity and performance (Federman, 2016). Furthermore, employee burn out also leads to increase in absenteeism due to sickness. Therefore, researchers strongly recommend that employers must have adequate programs and support for employees who are facing difficulty in managing balance between work and personal life (Agha, Azmi, and Irfan, 2017).

2.3 Impact of Work-life balance/imbalance

The most commonly cited factor that disturbs the work-life balance is workload. Every individual has a certain capacity to cater workload. Any increase in the workload that is beyond the capacity of employee leads to negative impact on performance and delivery of the professional responsibilities. It has been widely recognized that increase in workload is the main factor that increases stress and causes burnout (Belwal and Belwal, 2017).

Another important factor that has been commonly cited as one of the causes of imbalance in personal and professional life is work schedule. An employee is responsible to deliver the workload within specified timings. If the timings dedicated are insufficient then required workload is not delivered promptly. If the timings are inadequate or odd, the performance of the employee in terms of workload and quality of work is also compromised (Abubaker and Bagley, 2016).

Furthermore, Bae, et al., (2019) conducted a study to identify factors of work-life balance and concluded that one of the indicators of work-life balance is the time spent by an employee with his family and relatives, as well as with friends and social circle. If the work requirements and responsibilities do not allow employee to spend sufficient time, then there is a need to make improvements. However, the study also highlighted the fact that there are no accurate methods to gauge how much time is suitable for an employee. Women professionals need more time in the family as they are typically responsible to cater the needs of children and other family members. The number of children was also reported to be an important factor. There are also other factors that affect the time required by an employee to spend his family and remain satisfied.

Furthermore, Lau, et al., (2018) focused on determining the impact of work-life balance and argued that the time spent an employee in leisure and sporting activities can also be used as an indicator of work-life balance. The study elaborated that every employee needs to have certain level of leisure and sporting activities in order to remain physically and mentally healthy. If adequate leisure and sporting activities are not available to an employee, there is likely to be a compromise on mental and physical health and this ultimately affects performance and productivity of the employee.

Al-Barwani, (2016) pointed one of the main impacts of work life imbalance. The study conducted a large-scale survey about intentions to quit and employee turnover reasons and found that work life imbalance is one of the significant factors for employees to quit current jobs and look for other jobs in the market. In case of hospitality industry, the research indicated that work-life balance is one of the most important aspects of satisfaction of catering and housekeeping staff, especially women.

2.4 Role of Employer in Work-life balance

Majority of the researchers focusing on work-life balance suggest that it is in the interest of employer to offer strategic support to all employees to maintain healthy work-life balance. This is based on the rationale that employee satisfaction can be maximized by improving work-life balance and satisfaction of employees regarding professional and personal life. Employees with low satisfaction show low performance and productivity, higher absence, and higher turnover intentions. These outcomes of work life imbalance have negative impact on the firm and increase cost and compromise profitability (Federman, 2016).

Researchers have identified a wide variety of programs and support that can be used by employers to play their role in maintaining work-life balance. Since workload is the most important factor of work-life balance therefore, the most commonly cited strategy for employers is to engage the employees and involve them in determining adequate workload for them. If employees are involved in determining workload and managers are able to understand the degree to which an employee can deliver professional tasks and responsibilities efficiently and effectively, then there is positive impact on work-life balance (Hans, et al., 2015).

Another commonly cited strategy for employers is flexible work schedules. Naithani, (2016) concluded that flexible work schedules have become increasingly popular in professional world as a strategy to increase productivity and performance of employee, while also as a support strategy by employer to achieve better work-life balance. Flexible work schedules require managers to involve employees in determining the work timings and schedules. This way employees can distribute their time more adequately to both personal and professional life.

Another effective strategy as identified by Belwal and Belwal, (2017) is support from managers and colleagues. The support refers to the degree to which an employee receive help in managing workload. The study also concluded that teamwork and effective team building is critical to enhance support for a worker. Better work-life balance can be achieved provided that an employee gets help from manager and colleagues in delivering professional tasks and responsibilities.

Sporting and leisure facilities in office vicinity as well as memberships for such clubs were also identified by Akinyele, Peters, and Akinyele, (2016) as a strategy that can help an employee to maintain mental and physical health. Leisure and sporting activities are considered essential for every person irrespective of age to maintain mental and physical health. Lack of sporting and leisure activities causes negative impact on mental and physical capabilities of a person and ultimately performance is compromised. Many employers have developed facilities such as gyms and swimming pools that can be used by employees. However, many employers offer free membership or sponsored memberships to sporting and leisure clubs.

Another important factor is the leave and vacation policy of employers. It is critical that employers have adequate policy that can be used by employees to address emergency situation in the family such as medical emergency. Furthermore, the employer must also offer employee to have vacations that can be used for leisure or other family related activities. These are particularly important for female workers as they have typically higher responsibilities towards family and greater role and importance in family emergency and events (Federman, 2016).

2.5 Conceptual Framework

Based on the factors identified in previous sections following table summarizes the factors and impacts of work-life balance/imbalance and the typical strategies that represent the role of employer in supporting employee to achieve better work-life balance (WLB). The conceptual model below (see Fig. 1) has been used to develop questionnaire and formulate questions and statements for data collection purposes. A blank questionnaire has been presented in appendix to demonstrate how these factors are included in the questionnaire.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of determinants of Work-life balance

III. Methodology

The target population for this study was employees in the Middle East countries. Consequently, sampling was performed to assemble a reliable and representative sample. The study used snowball sampling method. The snowball sampling allow researcher to identify potential participants in personal contacts and then ask them refer to another participant. The research continues to gain referrals and gather data until a suitable sample size is achieved (Taylor, Bogdan, & DeVault, 2015).

In order to analyze and present data efficiently, this study conducted statistical analysis. The initial stage of the analysis covered the demographic summary of respondents (see Table 1). The second stage mainly covered the items of determining factors of WLB. A pilot test was done to evaluate the validity and reliability of the measures among 15 students and associates. They were asked to examine the clarity of questions, appropriateness of items measuring the variables. The reliability of the measures was tested by calculating Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of pre-tested responses. The values of the coefficients changed in the range of 0.72 - 0.81, which was accepted to be reliable. Because, the smallest value of Cronbach's Alpha was accepted to be 0.70 by Hair et al. (2006). The highest alpha value was accounted for Workload (WL) was 0.81, for Working hours (WH) was 0.78, and for Leaves and vacation (LV) 0.76, indicating that these determinants have highest reliability level if conceptualizing the WLB determinants. Table 2 shows the Cronbach's alpha values for the study variables. AMOS v.24 software package was used to analyze data with structural equation modelling (SEM). Measurement model was primarily assessed (also included Cronbach's alpha test for main survey items), followed by testing structural model (Hair et al., 1998).

IV. Data analysis and Results

4.1 Demographics

Demographic part of the analysis included gender, marital status, age, profession, ethnicity, education and other factors. Among the respondents, males are accounted for 65.3% compare to their female counterparts (34.7%). Majority of them was found to be married (59.7%) and they belong to 30-40 years old (40.9%). The details of the demographic analysis are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic profile of study subjects

<i>Profile</i>		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
Gender	Male	201	65.3
	Female	107	34.7
Marital status	Single	83	26.9
	Married	184	59.7
	Divorced	24	7.8
	Widowed	17	5.5
Age	< 30	112	36.4

	30-40	126	40.9
	> 40	70	22.7
Ethnicity	Saudi	105	34.1
	Jordanian	87	28.2
	Indian	63	20.5
	Filipino	29	9.4
	Others	24	7.8
Education	Diploma	75	24.4
	Bachelor	125	40.6
	Master	91	29.5
	Ph.D.	17	5.5
Sector of work	Public	122	39.6
	Private	186	60.4
Unit of work	Management	62	20.1
	Accounting	82	26.6
	Marketing	91	29.5
	Operator	34	11.0
	Human resources	26	8.4
	Others	13	4.2
Children	Yes	136	44.2
	No	114	37.0
	Not applicable	58	18.8
If yes, how many	1	89	28.9
	2	81	26.3
	3	117	38.0
	> 4	21	6.8
How old are they	0-5 years old	74	24.0
	5-10 years old	98	31.8
	10-20 years old	49	15.9
	> 20 years old	62	20.1
	Not applicable	25	8.1
Homeownership status	Owned	215	69.8
	Renting	93	30.2

4.2 Measurement model

Measurement model is considered as a vital fragment of data analysis process that is also denoted as the backbone of hypothesized relations among the study constructs in the aspect of SEM analysis. To assess the reliability

of the determinants of WLB, Cronbach's alpha was used (Hair et al., 1989). Reliability test is for assessing how consistent are the relations among the measuring items of each construct, as suggested by Hair et al. (2010). In the current study, four reliability level are defined based on the classification of Hinton et al. (2004). These levels are (1) low reliability less than 0.50 level, (2) moderate reliability between 0.50 and 0.70, (3) high reliability between 0.70 and 0.90, and (4) excellent reliability over 0.90.

Similar to the reliability done in pilot test, the alpha values for all variables were found to be highly reliable, while moderate reliability was recorded for FT (α - 0.68) and WD (α - 0.64). No excellent reliability was recorded. However, the findings allow to say that the reliability criteria of the study were met. In addition to the reliability test, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed for the aim of testing validity. Several items were eliminated as they were loaded on more than one factor and (or) had greater cross-loading from threshold level. The Kaiser-Meyer Olkin (KMO) measurement of sampling adequacy is 0.75, which is adequate level. In this regard, we could consider the variables to be valid for the factor analysis. Table 2 shows the details of CFA results.

Besides reliability and validity test, additional measures, including composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) were added to the measurement model testing. CR values over 0.70 and AVE values over 0.50 are acceptable (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988; Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 2. Mean, Standard deviation, factor loadings and Cronbach's alpha results

Construct item	Mean	SD	Standardized loadings	Cronbach's α
Working hours (WH)				0.78
WH1	2.14	0.97	0.72	
Workload (WKL)				0.81
WKL1	2.35	1.05	0.81	
Sports and Leisure Activities (SLA)				0.72
SLA1	2.09	1.01	0.74	
Job Switching (JS)				0.81
JS1	2.21	1.05	0.76	
Support from Managers and Colleagues (SMC)				0.73
SMC1	2.66	0.96	0.79	
SMC2				
Time for Family and Social Circle (TFSC)				0.72
SMC1	2.66	0.96	0.79	
Flexible Timings (FT)				0.68
FT1	2.95	0.88	0.74	
Membership with sporting and Social clubs (MSSC)				

MSSC1	2.87	1.04	0.77	
Leaves and Vacations (LV)				0.76
LV1	2.76	0.85	0.78	
Workload Determination (WD)				0.64
WD1	3.04	0.81	0.80	
Work-Life Balance (WLB)				0.73
WLB1	2.46	0.99	0.75	
WLB2	2.68	0.91	0.69	
WLB3	2.83	0.95	0.68	
WLB4	2.72	1.02	0.72	

Discriminant validity test, which measures the correlations among the determinants of WLB, showed adequate results (statistically significant). Discriminant validity test is employed with the square root of AVEs for each variable that must be higher than correlation coefficients.

Based on the correlation analysis, it can be said that employees' perceptions on SLA, WD, MSSC, and JS are mainly determining the WLB. The details of correlations among the variables are given in Table 3. In addition, AVE values were found to be higher than correlation coefficients as shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Correlation results

	WH	WKL	SLA	JS	SMC	TFSC	FT	MSSC	LV	WD	WLB
WH	0.74										
WKL	0.33	0.75									
SLA	0.21	0.32	0.71								
JS	0.06	0.27	0.16	0.76							
SMC	0.19	0.06	0.21	0.18	0.76						
TFSC	-0.4	0.54	0.41	0.35	0.42	0.75					
FT	0.04	0.35	0.29	0.19	-0.2	0.51	0.73				
MSSC	0.14	0.39	0.28	-0.1	0.05	0.48	0.03	0.72			
LV	0.28	0.28	0.16	0.64	0.18	0.08	-0.1	0.14	0.81		
WD	0.47	0.17	-0.1	0.39	0.02	0.01	0.07	0.19	0.04	0.74	
WLB	0.04	0.16	0.32	0.28	0.18	0.02	0.18	0.27	0.16	0.41	0.75

4.3 Structural model results

Testing the relationships between the most determining factors of employees' WLB in an organizational context shows that the surveyed employees are mainly concerned about working time, management and colleague

support, and time for family, while leisure and sport activities, and vacation-related factors are secondary or no importance in perceiving the balance between work and life being rational.

The most significant determinant of WLB was found to be TFSC ($\beta = 0.307^{***}$, $p < 0.001$), SMC ($\beta = 0.293^{***}$, $p < 0.001$), WH ($\beta = 0.287^{***}$, $p < 0.001$), WD ($\beta = 0.271^{**}$, $p < 0.01$), and WKL ($\beta = 0.262^{**}$, $p < 0.01$). The secondary factors determining WLB were identified as JS ($\beta = 0.196^*$, $p < 0.05$), FT ($\beta = 0.188^*$, $p < 0.05$), and LV ($\beta = 0.103^*$, $p < 0.05$). Finally, SLA ($\beta = 0.082$, $p = 0.297$) and MSSC ($\beta = -0.028$, $p = 0.441$) were found to be insignificant factors that determine the WLB perception of employees (see Fig. 2), meaning that employees in the organizational context in the Gulf are mainly concerned with time for family and social surroundings, changing their jobs if their current employers do not meet their requirements, longer working hours, and determination to their job tasks even though it is not necessary sometimes. On the contrary, it was found that Middle East employees are less concerned about how much time they can devote to sport and leisure activities, as well as being members of social and sport clubs. The details of the analysis are discussed broadly below.

Figure 2. Results of structural model of WLB and its determinants

V. Discussion

The current study investigated the work-life balance of employees in the Middle East and to explore the role of local businesses that potentially facilitate WLB among employees. Hence, a survey was conducted among employees including local residents and other nationalities to explore their perception about WLB and support from their employers to achieve it. The survey results indicated that the work-life balance of Middle East employees is disturbed. There is increased workload, long working hours which in turn cause stress and tiredness. Middle East employees are unable to manage family and social life and maintain adequate level of leisure and sporting activities. The research also concluded that there is high rate of employee turnover intention. Furthermore, there is also lack of support from Middle East employers. Employees are not engaged and involved in determination of work load and work schedules. There are lack of sporting and leisure facilities in Middle East workplaces and lack of support from managers and colleagues. There is also a need to improve leave and vacation policies. The SEM analysis further added that employees' WLB perceptions are mainly formed with working hours that they devote to their tasks, time that they can spend with family members, while also the support from managers and other colleagues, workload determination, and job switching. However, even though the employees are unable to manage their leisure and sport activities, they are less concerned about these. Therefore, employers are recommended to take into account the above-mentioned factors while assigning employees to the job tasks. This is highly risky for the companies in case they rely on the few employees who are highly vital for the firms. Losing them would cost a lot for the business operations.

The current research could eventually contribute to fulfilling an obligation in line with the working conditions in the countries in Arabic continent in reference with (1) building competitive knowledge economy by maintaining the current and attracting new talents through tailoring the policies for facilitating working conditions; (2) maintaining a cohesive society and preservation of identity through family stability and protection of family values. It must also be a strategic priority to advancement into a social development system by transforming from social care to social development, safeguarding integrated social policy-making, and high-quality of social services.

In one of the former studies, besides social and personal factors, religion-related factors were also covered in determining work life balance of employees (Abubaker & Bagley, 2016; Chandra, 2012). The precarious findings of the Palestinian study by Abubaker and Bagley (2016) provided a useful insight to the theoretical framework on why organizations must adopt WLB policies and practice towards women employees in particular. Western practice also emerged in the Arabic culture, where new forms of benefits are for helping workers' demands of work, cultural, religious, social and family-related concerns were identified. Hence, the current study combined with the newly validated factors (e.g., religious, country-specific) could highly contribute to the extension of theoretical framework to understand WLB in a certain country in future.

VI. Conclusion

The current research was managed to assess Middle East employees' work-life balance and found very useful insights on how hours of work and the relative stress are critically determining their work-life balance, alongside their intention to switch to another job in case their concerns are not taken into account, time for family members and social surroundings. Disguising between family obligations and expectations of the organization, as well as perpetual struggle to maintain a balance between work and family would have serious effects on the life of an individual (employee) by influencing his/her well-being and overall life quality. There is a widespread demand from employees for the right to balance work and home life in nowadays' hectic world where finding time for oneself appears to be not possible. Health and wellness programs can, for sure help working people to balance their individual and professional life. However, they alone are not likely to answer addressing the problems of imbalance. The challenges and difficulties of working people are multi-dimensional as evident from the literature review as well as the analysis results; consequently, they necessitate further probing to help working people in balancing their work and family life.

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